

Reliability-Growth Myths and Methodologies: A Critical View

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ABSTRACT

Reliability growth is a concept that is being used as the basis for planning equipment reliability tests, assessing reliability improvement for changing equipment configurations, and reliability predictions. This concept has been the subject of much discussion in the reliability community; over 80 articles can be found in the Annual Reliability Symposium Proceedings 1980-1991. In spite of this discussion, the underlying basis for the concept and its application has not been critically examined. In this paper it is asserted that reliability prediction is not a reasonable application of reliability growth concept, and that the various mathematical models introduced may not adequately describe the reliability growth process. Further understanding of the factors for test planning has not advanced beyond the rules of thumb that were proposed when the concept was initially introduced in 1964. The reliability community is challenged to reexamine the reliability growth concept and particularly how the concept is being applied.

INTRODUCTION

More and more judgments, based on applications of the concept of "reliability growth," are being made to decide if equipment (or systems) are likely to achieve their predicted reliability. Such judgments are particularly critical when the decision involves committing funds for equipment production.

The results of reliability growth tests are being increasingly used to support program decisions involving high cost, high reliability equipment.

Equipment with these characteristics present unique challenges in structuring reliability test programs that would provide sufficient data to determine equipment reliability. Traditional reliability demonstration tests are generally too expensive for high cost, high reliability equipment. Another situation where the reliability growth concept is increasingly being used involves reducing the time to bring an equipment into production. Here, traditional reliability demonstration test methods are viewed as unreasonably lengthening the development cycle.

The principal attraction for using the reliability growth concept to structure and interpret test results is that it appears to suggest an economical basis for judging equipment reliability, where there is changing equipment configuration. Changing equipment configuration is an expected activity of the engineering development cycle. Thus, decisions based on reliability growth make use of already planned engineering activities, thereby not requiring special reliability demonstration tests or lengthening the development schedule.

This author has been presented, on many occasions, with the arguments discussed above as the rationale for using the reliability growth concept to estimate or predict equipment reliability. These uses of reliability growth concept seemed at variance with what this author understood was the original objective of introducing the reliability growth concept. This led the author to examine the origin and basis of the reliability growth concept, reliability growth practices as they evolved over the years, and the evidence that supports the use of the reliability growth concept.

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The intent of this article is to provide the reader with sufficient information to draw his own conclusions with respect to proper applications of the reliability growth concept. Not provided in the article is a detailed description of the intricacies of structuring reliability growth program or the detailed mathematics associated with the reliability growth concept. Instead, the focus will be on the underlying principles and the applications of these principles. Of course this author has his own opinions (and maybe biases) which he will try to clearly label in the article.

BACK TO BASICS

"Reliability growth" is a term that has been part of the reliability community's jargon for over 25 years. The closest this author could find to formal a definition is in a Military Standard published in 1978, entitled "Reliability Growth Testing"¹ and a Military Handbook published in 1981 entitled "Reliability Growth Management."² Curiously, the definitions are not identical though they appear to encompass the same elements. The definitions have been combined and paraphrased as follows:

The positive improvement of reliability of equipment over time through the permanent removal of failure mechanism regardless of their source.

The concept of reliability growth is generally attributed to J.T. Duane, an engineer with the Aerospace Electronics Department of the General Electronic Company. In fact, many use the terms "Duane Model" or "Duane Curve" and it is understood to be referring to a reliability growth model or reliability growth curve. Duane is credited with providing "a growth model which easily utilizes and explains growth test results; and gives an early reliability indication of where the test is headed and how it's getting there."³

But, surprisingly Duane did not present his findings using the term "reliability growth" but rather as a "Learning Curve Approach to Reliability Monitoring"⁴ (emphasis added). Duane

observed⁵ that different complex electromechanical and mechanical systems "showed similar rates of improvement during system development." He further observed that the equipment development process could be characterized by "continuing improvements in design and refinements in both operating and maintenance." Based on his observations, Duane concluded that the equipment development process was a learning process and could be described by a "classical learning model equation."

A digression to learn about the learning curve. The learning curve theory is based on the observation that the cost of an item is a function of where in the manufacturing sequence the item was produced. The learning curve theory is usually attributed to J.P. Wright, who introduced a mathematical model describing a learning curve in a 1936 article in The Journal of Aeronautical Science titled "Factors Affecting the Cost of Airplane." Wright showed that the cumulative average direct labor input for an aircraft manufactured on a production line decreased in a predictable pattern. The decrease was obviously related to the increased proficiency (i.e., learning) of the manufacturing people on the line as they continued to perform the various repetitive tasks. The model that was published described the learning as an exponential function. One feature of the exponential function is that the relationship is linear when plotted on log-log graph paper.

Duane observed that the process associated with improving equipment reliability during the early stages of development "is one of learning through failures. Knowledge of the applicable learning curve would provide a means of measuring and predicting reliability during this period of change." He, too, suggested this learning could be mathematically described by an exponential function, which when plotted on log-log paper appeared as a straight line. Correction of unexpected failure modes was how the learning would come about. The learning is accomplished through a "test, analyze, and fix" (TAAF) process, and the term TAAF became associated with, and almost synonymous with reliability growth.

Table 1 summarizes the conditions for using a reliability learning curve approach:

Conditions Where Reliability Learning
Curve Concept Seems To Fit

- Models a single reliability development test activity
- Requires failure analysis and corrective actions as part of test activity
- Applies to equipment that operates continuously

TABLE 1

**WHAT CAN YOU DO WITH A RELIABILITY LEARNING
CURVE?**

Being able to mathematically describe the characteristics of a reliability learning process can potentially provide the basis for (1) planning reliability growth tests, (2) monitoring progress and estimating current (instantaneous) reliability, and (3) forecasting future reliability improvement (hence the term "reliability growth"). Each of these applications will be briefly explored, again with the emphasis on understanding whether there is a basis for the particular application.

The reliability growth mathematical model proposed by Duane (and others as discussed in the next section) relates reliability improvement to test time. From a reliability development test planning point of view, this relationship allows one to determine how much test time should be allocated in order to achieve a specified level of reliability improvement. Two parameters have to be selected to use the Duane reliability growth mathematical model: an initial starting point reliability value; and, an assumed improvement rate.

The initial starting point reliability value should somehow reflect how close the physical implementation of the design matches the predicted value. Generally, the practice has been to assume an initial starting point of 10% of the predicted equipment reliability value. However, this author has seen many instances where the initial reliability is in the order of 30% of the predicted equipment value. The higher initial starting reliability appears to reflect

better design practices (such as minimizing junction temperatures for integrated circuits), and using high-quality components in development hardware (primarily achieved through environmental stress screening).

The projected rate of reliability improvement - the slope of the learning curve - is said to be a function of the level of effort that will be applied in the test analyze and fix efforts. The general practice is to assume that the growth rate (curve slope) will be no higher than 0.5, with a moderate growth rate about 0.3, and a minimum growth rate of 0.1.

In any event, there does not appear to be specific studies or methodologies that provide guidance for a more "scientific" approach to selecting the reliability growth curve starting point or the projected growth rate. Of over 80 articles published in the Annual R&M Symposium Proceedings in the last 11 years,⁶ one article⁷ was found that attempted to develop a methodology that could be used to establish an initial starting point. Certainly factors such as number of units used in development test or number of engineers assigned to the test program could be expected to correlate to the expected growth rate. This lack of methodology is particularly surprising since the concept of reliability growth has been used to structure reliability growth test programs for about 20 years.

Equally surprising is the lack of attempts to specifically correlate the monitoring or predictive characteristics of the reliability growth curve with actual or demonstrated reliability. Many of the Annual R&M Symposium Proceedings articles reviewed in preparing to write this article provided examples of reliability growth programs. Very few (perhaps 2 or 3) attempt to discuss the correlation between the instantaneous reliability estimate calculated from the reliability growth curve with actual observed or separately demonstrated reliability.

While mechanically it would appear to be a simple matter to plug in test results and calculate instantaneous reliability, the actual practice is much more complicated. An example drawn from the author's experiences will serve to illustrate. Shown in Figure 1 is a typical reliability growth curve. The reliability growth curve line was drawn using a least squares fit. The associated reliability

growth curve statistics and possible interpretations are also shown in this figure. Figure 2 shows the test analyze and fix actions in terms of configuration change.

From the data at least 3 reliability estimates of the latest configuration can be made. An instantaneous reliability of about 86 hours at the time when the test was stopped (Point B). However, note from Figure 2 no configuration changes were made after the 400 hour test time. Therefore, the learning stopped and at the 400 hour point (Point A) the instantaneous reliability is about 65 hours. Another interpretation of the test results might be that the last 329 hours (points A - B) represented a reliability demonstration test of the latest configuration, yielding a "demonstrated" reliability of 49 hours. Other interpretations could also be made. For example, only counting the corrective actions that address design reliability failures (that is, exclude quality or manufacturing defects) would yield still another different estimate of equipment reliability.

Not addressed in this article, but seen by this author, is the sensitivity of the reliability growth prediction to the selection of data for establishing either the starting point or the slope of the growth curve. An extremely good article on interpreting reliability growth test results is "No - Growth Curves" by James M. Clarke in the Proceedings 1979 Annual R&M Symposium (page 407).

Notwithstanding the situations described in the preceding paragraphs, there seems to be ample evidence to support the application of a "learning curve" for monitoring reliability improvement over time. Of the articles cited in the index of Annual R&M Symposium Proceedings 1980-1991, approximately 15% have examples where reliability improvements followed a reliability growth curve. Rules that this author believes are appropriate for applying a reliability learning curve approach are summarized in Table 2:

Reliability Learning Curve Applications

Reasonable

- Determine approximate reliability test time requirements

- monitor rate of reliability improvement in test

Unreasonable

- Predicting equipment reliability, either current or future
- Used to combine different types of reliability tests

TABLE 2

COTTAGE INDUSTRY

Daune's observation appears to have served as the inspiration for introducing a number of different reliability growth mathematical models. Some of these are similar to Duane's, in that they are deterministic, while others treat reliability growth as a probabilistic. A further distinction is that Duane's model was developed for continuous operating equipment. Models have also been developed for modeling reliability growth where there are discrete events, for example, missile firings.

The Military Handbook on Reliability Growth Management⁸ lists 17 models which are intended to be used "as a guideline for choosing a candidate for a particular application." In addition, at least 10 models are described in the Annual Reliability and Maintainability Symposium Proceedings articles.

A search of the Annual R&M Symposium Proceedings articles indicates that very little attention has been paid to determining the accuracy of the proposed models. An example of how this might be done would be to use simulation techniques to compare strength and weakness of the proposed model to the true reliability.⁹

The number and different types of reliability growth models raises the question "Is this diversity necessary?" Duane was trying to describe a reliability engineering test process and show that it followed a predicable pattern. The underlying basis of this process is learning, in this case, redesign where there are unexpected failures. As with any physical process, randomness is to be expected. This in turn has led many mathematicians to propose a variety of

"curve fitting" models. Whether, in fact, these are better representations of the test, analyze, fix, and continue test process than the learning curve model proposed by Duane is questionable. Further, whether the learning process should be thought of as a probabilistic process is also questionable.

In the following table are the rules this author would follow in selecting a mathematical representation of the reliability development growth test:

Rules for Selecting a Reliability Growth Model

- Use simplest model possible
- Validate accuracy of model before using

TABLE 3

FINAL THOUGHTS

Clearly, the simplicity of the reliability growth concept has an attraction which lead to quick acceptance. Intuitively, the idea that one should be able to track reliability improvement over time in a structured testing process seemed right. Obviously, any well structured reliability test can and usually does identify components that do not meet predicted failure rates, particularly early in the equipment development cycle. The challenging question is whether limited reliability test data can be used as a basis for predicting equipment reliability, either for the current or a future configuration.

Equipment reliability predictions are determined from parameters that describe the reliability growth curve. These reliability predictions are calculated in a similar manner to the production unit cost developed for the production learning curve. However, there appears to be a significant practical difference in determining the points for these curves. The data used to plot a production learning curve -- direct production labor hours -- can be accurately determined. While the data used to plot a reliability growth curve, particularly the early points may not provide an accurate (high statistical

confidence) representation of the equipment reliability. Thus, it is not obvious that using reliability growth curve parameters, which are based on relatively inaccurate data, provides a dependable basis for equipment reliability prediction. This author believes that if a reliability prediction using growth test results is to be made, then the expected (predicted) equipment reliability must be the starting point. The challenge is how to couple the limited reliability growth test data to this starting point.

Hopefully, the notions in this article will encourage the reliability practitioner to reexamine the seemingly routine reliability growth practices.

REFERENCES

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BIOGRAPHY

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FAILURE NUMBER	TEST TIME (HOURS)	FAILURE CATEGORY	CONFIGURATION STATUS
1	8.00	RANDOM	
2	14.70	HARDWARE	CHANGE
3	63.57	RANDOM	
4	70.05	HARDWARE	CHANGE
5	85.72	RANDOM	
6	86.70	RANDOM	
7	170.55	MANF PROCESS	
8	241.92	MANF PROCESS	CHANGE
9	286.37	HARDWARE	CHANGE
10	400.00	RANDOM	
11	418.69	RANDOM	
12	424.19	HARDWARE	
13	506.24	HARDWARE	
14	569.22	RANDOM	
15	646.70	RANDOM	
16	705.07	HARDWARE	
17	729.22	RANDOM	

RELIABILITY GROWTH CORRECTIVE ACTIONS
FIGURE 2

DUANE Reliability Growth Curve

Figure 1. DUANE Reliability Growth Curve